

**ASSESSING THE EFFECTS OF BUILDING SPATIAL LAYOUT ON WINDOW TO WALL
RATIO IN TEMPERATE DRY CLIMATE OF NIGERIA**

Muhammad Aminu Musa

Department of Architecture, Faculty of Environmental Design, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria

ORCID NO: 0000-0003-4516-1281

ABSTRACT

The window-to-wall ratio (WWR) is very vital in achieving optimum Passive Indoor Thermal and Visual Comfort (PITVC) in buildings, particularly in tropical countries like Nigeria. Researchers have diverse views on the proper WWR for optimum PITVC in buildings. Some researchers have found out that buildings with WWR above 20% do not provide comfort temperature. Others have recommended 25% as the best WWR in the tropics, while ASHRAE 90.1 (2007) recommended a value of 24% as the optimum value for daylight and natural ventilation, and considered value below that as poor, and a value above 30% overheated. The International Energy Conservation Code recommends a different value of 30%. These and many more have not considered the effects of building spatial layout on WWR which this research is aimed at doing that in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria. It was achieved by using three (3) different building spatial layout (single-banked, double-banked, and open planned) and for each a range of values of WWR was used to determine the difference in daylight autonomy (DA), useful daylight illuminance (UDI₁₀₀₋₃₀₀₀), spatial daylight autonomy (sDA), operative temperature (OT) and relative humidity (RH). Data was collected from simulation of the prototype single-banked, double-banked, and open planned office buildings, using google Sketch-Up 2017 and open-studio simulation tool which was done on the hypothetical sites devoid of surrounding buildings and trees, in Jalingo, Minna, and Zaria. Data generated were then analysed using ANOVA, bar charts, column charts, graphs, and tables with significance threshold of 0.05. The findings revealed that, the best WWR are 20% and 15% for visual and thermal comfort in single-banked office buildings, 45% and 15% for double-banked and 30% and 26.5% for open-planned office buildings respectively. When the values of daylight metrics and thermal comfort indicators were ranked together, 20% was found to be the most compromised value for single-banked, 45% for the double-banked and 30% for the open-planned office buildings. One-way MANOVA was used and a statistically significant difference was obtained, $F(30, 210) = 8.634$, $p < .0000$; Pillai's $\Lambda = 2.761$, partial $\eta^2 = .552$ for single-banked, $F(20, 296) = 18.828$, $p < .0000$; Pillai's $\Lambda = 2.240$, partial $\eta^2 = .560$ for double-banked and $F(20, 136) = 10.187$, $p < .0000$; Pillai's $\Lambda = 2.399$, partial $\eta^2 = .600$ for open-planned office buildings. The implication of this study is that the three (3) building spatial layout must have different framework to achieve PITVC in temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

Keywords: Building spatial layout, Thermal comfort, Visual comfort, Window to wall ratio.

1.0 Introduction

The window-to-wall ratio (WWR) is the measure of the percentage area determined by dividing the area of the building's total window openings by the area of the wall's exterior envelope. Many researchers have come up with different values of optimum WWR such as Kandari, et al., (2011) and Nigerian Building Energy Efficiency Code (Solid, 2017) who recommended 25% and 20% as the best WWR in the tropics respectively. Budhiyanto (2017), showed that, WWR above 20% doesn't provide comfort temperature. Another study by ASHRAE 90.1 (2007) has recommended a value of 24% as the optimum value for daylight and natural ventilation, and considered value below that as poor, while a value above 30% overheated. However, in ASHRAE 90.1 (2010) it was changed to 40% and in 2022 edition it recommends 20% for the mid-rise buildings (Goel et al., 2014). The International Energy Conservation Code (2012 IECC) recommends a different value of 30% as the optimum (Makela, Williamson & Makela, 2011), while a study carried out in the temperate dry climate of Singapore found out 24% as

the optimum (Ahsan, 2009; Liping, & Hien, 2007). Another research conducted by Shebl (nd) showed Egypt is 20%, while Rashid, Malik, and Ahmad (2016) have found a range of 20% to 30% as the optimum in Lahore Pakistan. Harmtia and Magyarb, (2015) gave a different value, with 30% for east and west orientated offices; 25% for south-oriented offices; and 20% for the corridor on the north elevation. These and many more have not considered the effects of building spatial layout on.

The aim of this study is to assess the effects of spatial layout on WWR for PITVC in midrise office buildings in temperate dry climate of Nigeria. It was done by using three (3) different building spatial layouts and for each a range of values of WWR was used to determine the difference in daylight autonomy (DA), useful daylight illuminance (UDI₁₀₀₋₃₀₀₀), spatial daylight autonomy (sDA), operative temperature (OT) and relative humidity (RH). These brought about the following hypothesis: The null hypothesis (H₀) states that, the mean effect of building spatial layout on WWR for PITVC is significantly the same, while the alternative hypothesis (H₁) states that, the mean effect of building spatial layout on WWR for PITVC is significantly different for at least of the building spatial layout.

There are many ways to classify office buildings in architecture as noted by Musa (2022) of which classification based on access to light be classified as either closed-planned or opened planned. The closed-planned is sub-classified as single-banked and double-banked office buildings as indicated in Figure 1.1.

The procedure used in conducting the research is based on the Daylighting Monitoring Protocols and Procedures for Buildings, 1997, Monitoring Procedures for Assessment of Daylighting Performance of Buildings, 2001, Illuminating Engineering Society (2012), 2015 International Energy Conservation Code, USA, and ASHRAE standards 55 (2020).

Figure 1. 1. Classification of office buildings

Source: Musa, (2022)

2.0 Methodology

The study used quantitative research design using an explorative design approach as well as an experimental research strategy through simulation method to assess the various range of WWR values and their corresponding values of DA, UDI₁₀₀₋₃₀₀₀, sDA, OT and RH. The Iterative prototypes of Federal Secretariat (single-banked), Bank of Industry (double-banked) and BUK Senate Building (open-plan) were modeled in google sketch up 2017 and simulated in OpenStudio from January to December 2018 on the hypothetical sites devoid of surrounding buildings and trees, in Jalingo, Minna, and Zaria, and their mean values were used. These buildings were selected due to the fact that the Federal Secretariat and Bank of Industry buildings are replicated all over the temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

Six (6) sets of offices (48) were used for the simulation of single and double-banked office buildings while eight (8) sets of the open-plan office buildings were used. The mean of each floor was then evaluated. Data generated were then analysed using MANOVA statistical tool with a significance value of 0.05, bar charts, column charts, graphs, and Tables to find out the effects of a mid-rise office building spatial layout on the passive PITVC in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

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Plate I. Prototypes of double-banked, single-banked and open-plan midrise offices (from left to right).

3.0 Findings and Discussion

The simulations of single-banked, double-banked and open-planned office buildings, with R-value of $2.08 \text{ m}^2\text{K/W}$ and Azimuth angle of 11.5° were done and the results are presented in Tables 3.1, 3.2, and 3.3 respectively.

Table 3.1. Simulation results for the effects of WWR on DA, sDA and UDI in a single-banked mid-rise office building, in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

WWR	0.15	0.195	0.200	0.220	0.240	0.300	0.400
DA	71	80	80	81	82	84	84
UDI	82	79	79	77	75	68	53
sDA	94.04	95.64	95.71	96.25	96.39	96.93	97.5

The results shows that in the simulated single-banked office building only one out of seven conditions fulfilled the benchmarks as put forward by Illuminating Engineering Society (IES, 2012) and Architectural Energy Corporation (AEC, 2013) which recommends a DA value of 60% of the work plane illuminance; $UDI_{100-3000}$ of 80% and sDA of 75% in office space. However none of the conditions fulfilled the benchmarks in double-banked and open-planned office buildings as indicated in table 3.2 and 3.3 respectively.

Table 3.2. Simulation results for the effects of WWR on DA, sDA and UDI in a double-banked mid-rise office building, in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

WWR	0.15	0.2	0.24	0.3	0.40	0.425	0.45
DA	19	27	33	42	57	60	63
UDI	59	68	70	70	70	70	70
sDA	32.8	40.89	55.75	71.05	77.45	83.15	83.9

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Table 3.3. Simulation results for the effects of WWR on DA, sDA, and UDI in an Open-plan mid-rise office building, in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

WWR	0.15	0.2	0.24	0.265	0.3
DA	26	42	53	61	71
UDI	79	81	80	79	78
sDA	52.7	77.1	89	89	94.4

It was also observed that as the WWR increases so the DA increases while the UDI decreases. The rank and percentile was used to evaluate the most appropriate WWR for visual comfort and the most compromised value for single-banked, double-banked and open-planned were found to be 20%, 45% and 30% respectively as shown in table 3.4 to 3.6. The results has explained the findings of Shebl (nd) and ASHRAE 90.1, (Goel et al., 2014), which are incompliance with single-banked office buildings, while the 2012 International Energy Conservation (Makela, Williamson & Makela, 2011) in compliance with the open-planned office buildings.

The results has also revealed that single-banked office buildings have the highest percentage of annual daytime hours that a defined position on the earth is more than an agreed illumination level, followed by open-planned and then double banked as indicated in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1. Comparison of the the effects of spatial layout on WWR for DA

It is also true for SDA and UDI as indicated in Figure 3.2 and 3.3.

Figure 3.2. Comparison of the the effects of spatial layout on WWR for sDA

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Figure 3.3. Comparison of the the effects of spatial layout on WWR for UDI

The simulation was done for the effects of WWR on operative temperature and relative humidity and the results revealed that the best WWR for minimum operative temperature and maximum relative humidity for single-banked, double-banked and open-planned are 15%, 15%, and 26.5% respectively as shown in Figure 3.4, 3.5 and 3.6 respectively.

Figure 3.4. WWR for minimum operative temperature and maximum relative humidity in a single-banked office building.

Figure 3.5. WWR for minimum Operative temperature and Relative humidity in a double-banked office building

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Figure 3.6. Compromised WWR for Operative temperature and Relative humidity in Open-plan office building

The values of daylight metrics and thermal comfort indicators were ranked together and the most compromised values of 20% 45% and 30% are found for single-banked, double-banked and open-planned buildings respectively as shown in table 3.4, 3.5 and 3.6 respectively.

Table 3.4. Ranking of the WWR for PITVC of single-banked office buildings

WWR	DA	UDI	sDA	Daylight Comfort	Thermal Comfort	PITVC	Remark
15	5 th	1 st	7 th	6 th	1 st	4 th	20% is the most appropriate WWR for PITVC.
19.5	4 th	2 nd	6 th	2 nd	2 nd	2 nd	
20	4 th	2 nd	5 th	1 st	3 rd	1 st	
22	3 rd	3 rd	4 th	3 rd	4 th	3 rd	
24	2 nd	4 th	3 rd	4 th	5 th	5 th	
30	1 st	5 th	2 nd	5 th	6 th	6 th	
40	1 st	6 th	1 st	7 th	6 th	7 th	

Table 3.5. Ranking of the WWR for PITVC in double-banked office buildings

WWR	DA	UDI	sDA	Daylight Comfort	Thermal Comfort	PITVC	Remark
15	7 th	3 rd	7 th	7 th	1 st	3 rd	45% is the most appropriate WWR for PITVC.
20	6 th	2 nd	6 th	6 th	3 rd	4 th	
24	5 th	1 st	5 th	5 th	3 rd	3 rd	
40	3 rd	1 st	3 rd	3 rd	3 rd	2 nd	
45	1 st	1 st	1 st	1 st	2 nd	1 st	

Source: Author, 2022

Table 3.6 Ranking of the WWR for PITVC in Open-plan office buildings

WWR	DA	UDI	sDA	Daylight Comfort	Thermal Comfort	PITVC	Remark
15	5 th	3 rd	4 th	4 th	2 nd	3 rd	30% was chosen as the most appropriate WWR for PITVC.
20	4 th	1 st	3 rd	3 rd	2 nd	2 nd	
24	3 rd	2 nd	2 nd	2 nd	3 rd	2 nd	
26.5	2 nd	3 rd	2 nd	2 nd	1 st	1 st	
30	1 st	4 th	1 st	1 st	2 nd	1 st	

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The results have explained the findings of *Budhiyanto (2017)*, who showed that buildings with WWR above 20% do not provide a Comfortable temperature, to mean of single-banked buildings.

3.1 Hypothesis Testing

H_{01} : The null hypothesis states that, the mean effects of spatial layout on WWR for PITVC are significantly the same.

To test the hypothesis, the data were tested for skewness and kurtosis and found to be within the acceptable range of values as specified by George and Mallery, (2010). The one-way MANOVA was used to test if the office building spatial layout differs from each other significantly in one or more WWR for PITVC. **The homogeneity of variance-covariance matrices was tested for single-banked, double-banked and open-planned office buildings using Box's Test of Equality of Covariance Matrices and the Box' M** valued obtained were 47.866, 329.073 and 173.937 with a p-value of .049. These were interpreted as non-significant based on Huberty and Petosky's (2000) guidelines (p must be less than 0.005 to be significance). Therefore the covariance matrices of the dependent variables were equal across groups for MANOVA. It was then tested and a statistically significant difference was obtained, $F(30, 210) = 8.634, p < .0000$; Pillai's $\Lambda = 2.761$, partial $\eta^2 = .552$ for single-banked, $F(20, 296) = 18.828, p < .0000$; Pillai's $\Lambda = 2.240$, partial $\eta^2 = .560$ for double-banked and $F(20, 136) = 10.187, p < .0000$; Pillai's $\Lambda = 2.399$, partial $\eta^2 = .600$ for open-planned office buildings.

A homogeneity for variance assumptions was tested for all the five PITVC variables before conducting a series of tests between the subject effects. Based on a series of Levene's F tests, it was considered satisfactorily. A Series of one-way ANOVA's on each of the PITVC variables was conducted as a follow-up test to the MANOVA. The results for the **single-banked** turn out to be statistically significant in all the DA ($F(6, 42) = 59.39; p < .000$; partial $\eta^2 = .895$), UDI ($F(6, 42) = 271.793; p < .0000$; partial $\eta^2 = .975$), and sDA ($F(6, 42) = 66.778; p < .0000$; partial $\eta^2 = .905$). The other two were not, because they have fallen out of the span of -2 to +2 as the acceptable values for skewness and kurtosis, as specified by George & Mallery, (2010). So also the results for the double-banked buildings turn out to be statistically significant in all the DA ($F(4, 75) = 319.351; p < .000$; partial $\eta^2 = .945$), UDI ($F(4, 75) = 25.073; p < .0000$; partial $\eta^2 = .572$), sDA ($F(4, 75) = 330.158; p < .0000$; partial $\eta^2 = .905$), OT ($F(4, 75) = 5.1761; p < .0000$; partial $\eta^2 = .235$) and RH ($F(4, 75) = 5.413; p < .0000$; partial $\eta^2 = .224$). The open-planned office building has also turned out to be statistically significant in all the DA ($F(4, 35) = 87.586; p < .000$; partial $\eta^2 = .909$), UDI ($F(4, 35) = 2.183; p < .0000$; partial $\eta^2 = .200$), sDA ($F(4, 35) = 89.114; p < .0000$; partial $\eta^2 = .911$), OT ($F(4, 35) = 3.713; p < .0000$; partial $\eta^2 = .298$) and RH ($F(4, 35) = 5.438; p < .0000$; partial $\eta^2 = .383$).

A series of post-hoc analysis using Fisher's LSD was performed for single-banked office building to examine individual mean differences comparison across all the seven different WWR and five PITVC variables. The result revealed that, for DA, UDI, and sDA, all WWR was statistically significant with one another and the opposite was also true for operative temperature and relative humidity because they were nonparametric data. A Kruskal-Wallis test was therefore used to compare the effects of WWR on operative temperature having fallen out the span of -2 to +2 as the acceptable values for skewness and kurtosis, as specified by George & Mallery, (2010). It showed a statistically significant difference in operative temperature score among the different WWR, $\chi^2(5) = 29.62, p = 0.0000$, with a mean rank Operative temperature of 9.75 for 0.15 WWR, 16.69 for 0.195 WWR, 22.63 for 0.2 WWR, 26.94 for 0.22 WWR, 33.94 for 0.24 WWR, 45.13 for 0.3 and 42.44 for 0.4 WWR. Moreover, a series of post-hoc analysis using Fisher's LSD were performed to examine individual mean differences comparison across all the five (5) different WWR and five PITVC variables in each of the double-banked and open-planned office buildings, the results revealed that, all the five (5) WWR were statistically significant with one another.

4.0 Conclusion

The null hypothesis is therefore rejected and the study concludes that building spatial layout has significant influence on the window to wall ratio for the passive indoor thermal and visual comfort in temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

5.0 Implication of the study

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The study recommends that the single-banked, double-banked, and open-plan buildings must have 20%, 45% and 30% WWR to achieve passive thermal and visual comfort in temperate dry climate of Nigeria. This means that, each should have a different framework for PITVC in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

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